

IDENTIFICATION THE MAJOR MODERN APPLICATION OF FARM MACHINERY TOOLS BY THE FARMERS

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Abstract

This study surveys the advancement of horticultural automation, especially farm haulers, in India. In doing as such, it gives a few harsh marks of the degree of motorization (especially the spread of farm truck use) at various recorded stages, accentuating that India's encounters up to 1990 are essentially as significant as the illustrations from that point forward. The paper features the development of assorted examples of custom-employing administration arrangement, as well as heterogeneity in the speed of automation development across locales and agro natural zones. It additionally sums up the advancement of key related approaches in India that are probably going to have impacted farm hauler imports, supply, funding, producing, and related information sources like fuel and power.

Keywords: Advancement, Automation, Motarization, Accentuating, Heterogeneity.

Introduction:

Agriculture is the backbone of Indian economy as it provides direct employment to about 70% of the working people and a source of livelihood for them. Indian agriculture is now becoming more and more mechanized. Modern farm mechanization enhances the agricultural production besides assuring better quality of work. The adoption of modern farm machinery/ tools like tractors, power tillers, combine harvester, irrigation pumps, drip irrigation etc. has brought a drastic change in Indian agriculture, resulting in replacement of traditional means and methods used by the farmers for different operations. It was generally believed that the benefit of modern farm technology have been restricted only to the farmers with large land holdings, depriving the small and marginal farmers of its benefits.

As per the 4th Advance Estimates of Production of Food grains for 2019-2020, total food grain production was estimated 264.77 million tones. Being the largest source of employment and income and income to millions of people, it also provides a vast market for our industrial products. Despite the focus on industrialization, agriculture remains a dominant sector of Indian economy both in terms of contribution of gross domestic products as well as source of employment to millions across the country.

Modern farm mechanization is a term used for new and improved techniques, machineries, tools and implements in the field of agriculture. Modern farm mechanization enhances the farmer's productivity by reducing the time of operations and providing the better quality work. There was a time when the agriculture was wholly dependent on the human and animal efforts, but now with the advancement in farm technology, agriculture production has increased. The techniques have been used for the purpose of land preparation, crop cultivation, irrigation, threshing, processing, storage and protection. Farm mechanization plays a vital role in terms of yielding higher farm returns by adopting new technologies.

It reduces dependency on the laborers, reduces the physical power, increases productivity, maximizing profitability and provides indirect employment. In the wake of green revolution the Indian farmers adopted various modern agricultural technologies. The adoption of machineries like tractors, power tillers, combine harvester, irrigation pumps sets, etc.

Modernization has been a worldwide phenomenon approximately since 18th century. Agricultural modernization is an important aspect of modernization and also an important interdisciplinary component of world modernization. Since prosperous agriculture is considered to be the most crucial base for economic development particularly in the less developed countries, the only viable option for them is to continue to enhance the productivity of land and labor in agriculture. Increased productivity in agriculture has been achieved in several parts of the world mainly by modernizing agriculture (Atkociuniene and Zemeckis, 2015). Today, most farms and ranches are small. But farms are getting larger and more concentrated. Increasingly, farmers contract with large business operations, called agribusinesses. These

businesses purchase the farmers' crops or animals and produce the food that we recognize on grocery store shelves. Farmers who do business in this way say that they reduce their risk of losing money because they are guaranteed a buyer that will offer them a known price for their crops or animals. Other farmers sell their products themselves elsewhere, such as on commodities exchanges-trading centers, similar to stock markets where prices often are determined by worldwide supply and demand for the products. A variety of factors, such as worldwide market conditions, may lower or raise the prices that farmers receive. Because farmers have little control over pricing, keeping down the costs of production is especially important. Modern farmers use a wide range of techniques to maximize production and reduce costs (Dohm, 2005).

Thus, the present study reveals an analysis of socio economic profile of the respondents. Therefore, it is essential to have the comprehensive data of farm management studies to obtain the correct solution and also in helping the farmers in decision making.

Materials and Methods:

The study entitled "Identification the major modern application of farm machinery tools by the farmers" was undertaken to identify the modern farm machinery tools used in agriculture.

Study design:

Multistage stratified random sampling procedure was adopted for the present investigation to select the ultimate unit of the sample.

Place of the study

The present study was conducted in Prayagraj district, U.P. Prayagraj district has been selected for present course of investigation.

Sampling Procedure:

Selection of districts: Prayagraj district of U.P is selected purposively for the study

Selection of block: There are 20 blocks out of that Chaka block was purposively selected for present study. Chaka is a block in the Prayagraj district of U.P.

Selection of villages: A list of villages was obtained from the block office on the basic of population 5% villages was selected randomly.

Selection of respondents: A list of respondents was taken from the village Pradhan/CDO of the respective village/ block. The respondent was selected 5% randomly of their population. The selected respondent was arranged in ascending orders and category was divided on the basis of their land holding.

Data collection:The data for the percent study was collected from both primary and secondary sources.

Primary Data: primary data were collected using survey method. To conduct survey among respondents, well-structured questionnaire was prepared and collected information by meeting 50 paddy cultivators. Respondents for the present study was chosen by using random sampling technique.

Secondary Data: The secondary data was collected from the various articles, journals, books, websites and other internet sources.

Analysis of Data:

Statistical methods involved in carrying out a study include planning, designing, collecting data, analyzing, drawing meaningful interpretation and reporting of the research findings.

The statistical analysis was carried out for each observed character using MS-Excel and SPSS. The following statistical analysis was used to analyses the data.

Results and Discussion:

The study entitled “**Identification the major modern application of farm machinery tools by the farmers**” was undertaken to identify the modern farm machinery tools used in agriculture.

Table 1 Modern Farm Mechanization-has a significant role in the growth of agriculture in the area. The modern agricultural implements

and techniques are used by the farmers in seasonal periods as well as in whole year for various farming operations at various frequencies. The use of different tools/implements depends on the requirements of the farmers. The Table 4.8 shows the distribution of frequency of using these modern agricultural implements and techniques.

It is clear from the data that a majority of the data (92% and more were using Modern Agricultural Implements and Techniques like Poly- Houses, Power Tillers Power Sprayers and Check Basin and most frequently, however all the were rarely found to use Threshers. Similarly, Tractors and other Implements like Secateurs, Pruning Saw and Seed Drillers etc. were rarely used by a substantial percentage of them.

Table – 1 Frequency distribution based on the use

Sr. No.	Implements/ Technology	Respondents	Marginal	Small	Semi-medium	Medium	Large	Percent [%]
1.	Tractors	27	0	5	9	13	0	22.5%
2.	Power Tillers	20	0	4	8	8	0	16.67%
3.	Power Sprayers	15	0	1	5	9	0	12.5%
4.	Check Basin	20	0	3	10	7	0	16.67%
5.	Poly Houses	10	0	0	2	8	0	8.33%
6.	Threshers	15	0	2	6	7	0	12.5%
7.	Others [Pruning Saw and Seed Drillers etc.]	13	0	1	5	7	0	10.83%
	Total	120	0	16	45	59	0	100%

From the table it could be seen that Tractors were Percent highest 22.5 per cent. Above the table 16.67 Per cent Power Tillers farm machinery tools used by the farmers. It is clear from the data that a majority of the data 12.5 Percent Power Sprayers were using Modern Agricultural Implements and Techniques. And 16.67 Percent Check Basin, 8.33 Percent Poly Houses, 12.5 Percent Threshers and Others [Pruning Saw and Seed Drillers etc.] 10.83 Percent.

Chart 1 Frequency distribution based on the use.

The respondents were asked about the sources of information consulted by them for obtaining information about modern agricultural implements. The data have been presented in table 2.

Table 2 Sources of information consulted

Sr. No.	Sources Consulted	Frequency/Respondents	Percent[%]
1.	Mass Media	15	12.5
2.	University Scientists	20	16.67
3.	Extension Functionaries of the state department	13	10.83
4.	Fellow farmers	35	29.17
5.	Relatives and friends	27	22.5
6.	Workshops /Seminars/training camps	10	8.33
	Total	120	100%

Satisfaction with the modern tools used:

It can be drawn in table 3 that the respondent’s satisfaction level with the use of modern farm tools is 86 percent, whereas the respondents who are not satisfied with the use of modern farm tools is 14 percent,

hence the data based on response of the farming community is that most of the farmers are satisfied with the use of modern farm tools.

Table 3 Satisfaction with the use of modern tools

Satisfaction	No. of respond	Percentage
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Status	ents	
Yes	100	83.33
No	20	16.67
Total	120	100

Summary and Conclusion:

It is clear from the data that a majority of the data (92% and more were using Modern Agricultural Implements and Techniques like Poly- Houses, Power Tillers Power Sprayers and Check Basin and most frequently, however all the were rarely found to use Threshers. Similarly, Tractors and other Implements like Secateurs, Pruning Saw and Seed Drillers etc. were rarely used by a substantial percentage of them.

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